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Monitoring woody landscape features in Dutch rural landscapes

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ABSTRACT

Woody landscape features (WLF) declined sharply in the Netherlands in the twentieth century, with negative consequences on biodiversity and ecosystem services. EU and national policies aim to reverse this trend. However, recent assessments of WLF in the Netherlands are lacking. Ecosystem Accounts (EA) could support the monitoring of WLF but data on WLF in the Dutch EA is incomplete. Therefore this paper has the dual objective to assess WLF in the Netherlands, and to analyse how WLF can be monitored with EA, complemented with Laser Imaging Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) data. We used three Dutch rural regions, with different landscape characteristics and WLF densities, as case studies. We assessed the current extent and recent trends of WLF with LiDAR data, and compared the LiDAR based estimates with existing data in the Dutch EA. LiDAR based results indicated a density of WLF about 15% higher than the Dutch EA. However, even the WLF density as measured with LiDAR does not reach the EU and national policy targets for agricultural land in two of the three study areas. Moreover, both LiDAR data and the Dutch EA indicated that the area of WLF decreased over 2011–2021 in all study areas. LiDAR data can be used to enhance the Dutch EA for the purpose of monitoring WLF in rural landscapes, allowing a more complete representation of small features in agricultural fields and surrounding areas, such as farmyards, canals and road verges. Further efforts are needed to monitor and maintain Dutch WLFs.

1. Introduction

Landscape features are small natural or semi-natural areas in rural landscapes that are not used for agricultural production. They include natural or semi-natural vegetation (e.g. hedges, trees), surface water (e.g. ponds, ditches) and anthropogenic structures (e.g. terrace walls). Landscape features are an essential component of the identity of European rural landscapes (Arnaiz-Schmitz et al., 2018). They offer breeding sites, shelters and food to farmland species (Carlier and Moran, 2019) and provide a wide range of ecosystem services (ESs) (Drexler et al., 2021; England et al., 2020; Montgomery et al., 2020; Weninger et al., 2021). However, landscape features have drastically declined in the EU in the twentieth century due to land consolidation, the substitution of hedges with barbed wire and urbanization (Koomen et al., 2007; Robinson and Sutherland, 2002), with negative consequences on farmland biodiversity and ESs supply (Denac and Kmecl, 2021). To counter this, the EU biodiversity strategy for 2030 aims to maintain existing and plant new landscape features, in order to achieve a minimum of 10 % of

agricultural land under high diversity landscape features by 2030 (European Commission, 2020). Consequently, the enhancement of landscape features is one of the main environmental objectives of the European Nature Restoration Law (European Union, 2024) and of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) legislation for 2023–2027. The share of agricultural land covered with landscape features is also an indicator of the CAP performance (European Commission, 2018).

However, mapping of landscape features remains a challenge that prevents monitoring whether these EU policy targets are achieved. EU-wide datasets are available but have limitations (Czucz and Baruth, 2022): field samples detect detailed landscape feature types of small size but do not have a wall to wall coverage, while the Copernicus land monitoring service maps do not detect small elements, such as woody features with a width less than three meters (Kleeschulte et al., 2023). Few EU countries have datasets specifically aimed to monitor landscape features, and available national topography maps do not provide all inputs required for delineating and monitoring landscape features. A recent review on the EU INSPIRE geoportals found relevant datasets in

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two third of EU countries but mostly on wet landscape features, whereas only five countries had specific datasets for woody landscape features (WLF) (Czúcz et al., 2022).

Also in the Netherlands farming intensification and the accompanying land consolidation resulted in the loss of landscape features (van Apeldoorn et al., 2013). It was estimated that more than half of landscape features have disappeared from rural landscapes during the twentieth century (Koomen et al., 2007). WLF, such as forest patches, hedgerows, tree rows and isolated trees declined the most (Koomen et al., 2007). To address this decline, a Dutch national plan (Hagendoorn et al., 2021) for landscape features was conceived by a coalition of stakeholders from the public and private sector. This plan aims to increase the share of total area of rural landscapes covered by landscape features to 10 % by 2050, with WLF contributing to half of this target (5 % of the total rural landscapes area) (Hagendoorn et al., 2021). Whereas the EU policy target focusses on agricultural land (i.e. arable land, permanent grassland and permanent crops), the Dutch national plan target covers the whole rural area, including agricultural land but also other land uses (e.g. road verges, farmyards, settlements) within rural areas. In 2016, the total coverage of WLF in the Netherlands was estimated to be about 117,000 ha, corresponding to 3.5 % of the rural area (van Doorn et al., 2016).

Despite the importance of WLF in agri-environmental policy and their decline in the past, there are gaps in the monitoring of WLF in the Netherlands. No recent evaluation of changes in WLF coverage has been undertaken since the works of Koomen et al. (2007), which covered the period 1990–2003, and van Doorn et al. (2016) whom did not assess temporal changes. It is therefore not known whether the loss of WLF is continuing and how much effort is needed to meet the policy targets, neither in the agricultural areas nor in other land uses within rural areas. The most complete dataset recording WLF over the whole country is the National Topographic (Top10NL) data (Kadaster, 2024; van Doorn et al., 2016), updated every year, with records of forest patches, hedgerows and tree lines, as well as isolated trees. However, comparing this data with exhaustive records for a sample of small landscapes, van Doorn et al. (2016) found that forest patches were covered but that one third of hedgerows/tree lines and 80 % of isolated trees were missing in the Top10NL data. Other datasets provide exhaustive records, but for only a sample of landscapes (LandschappenNL, 2024), or only record features declared by landowners to receive subsidies (RVO, 2023).

Another possibility to enhance the monitoring of WLF in the Netherlands is the System of Environmental Economic Accounting Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA EA) framework. The SEEA EA is an integrated statistical framework for organizing biophysical data on ecosystem assets and services (Hein et al., 2020a). Ecosystem accounts (EA) track changes over time of ecosystems extent (extent accounts), condition (condition accounts) and services flows (ES accounts) in a spatially explicit manner and with a full coverage of the national territory (United Nations et al., 2024). The Netherlands is one of the most advanced countries in SEEA EA implementation (Hein et al., 2020b; Statistics Netherlands & WUR, 2022). In particular, ecosystem extent accounts have been compiled over the period 2013–2022 with a yearly update frequency and comprise 52 ecosystem type classes, including forest and hedgerows. Moreover, ecosystem condition accounts include the density of woody linear features in ecosystem types as condition variable. Monitoring WLF with the SEEA EA framework could have several potential advantages: (1) accounts are continuously updated by Statistics Netherlands, the Dutch statistical office, in consistent time series; (2) WLF are integrated in ES assessments, which allows to estimate ESs delivered by WLF and the influence thereof of WLF changes; (3) time series of ecosystem extent accounts combined with land use data can provide insights on the drivers of WLF changes.

However, at the moment, forest patches and linear features (hedgerows and tree lines) in the Dutch ecosystem extent accounts map are derived mainly from the Top10NL data and therefore incomplete (van Doorn et al., 2016). This data gap could be filled using airborne Laser

Imaging Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) data. While first LiDAR acquisition campaigns took six to seven years to cover the Netherlands, the frequency of updates has recently increased to three years, which makes it possible to use this data for monitoring purpose. Several studies have demonstrated the use of airborne LiDAR data for mapping WLF in EU countries (Broughton et al., 2021; Estrada et al., 2017; Lucas et al., 2019; Luscombe et al., 2023), but those studies did not assess the use of LiDAR data time series for monitoring purposes.

Therefore, this paper has the dual objective to assess the current state and recent trends of WLF in the Netherlands, and to analyse how WLF can best be monitored with EA complemented with LiDAR data. The study is carried out in three regions of the Netherlands with different landscape characteristics and densities of WLF: Rivierenland, Zeeland and Limburg. We address four specific research questions: (1) What is the current extent and recent trends of WLF based on LiDAR data?, (2) What is the current extent and recent trends of WLF based on EA data?, (3) What are the differences between LiDAR-based and EA data?, and (4) How do the current state and recent trends of WLF differ between agricultural land and other land uses?

We estimate the current state and recent changes of WLF in the three regions, using, first, LiDAR data (<https://www.ahn.nl>), and second, EA data. Next, we analyse the differences between these two data sources to assess how LiDAR data could complement EA. Furthermore, we integrate LiDAR based WLF maps with the ecosystem extent accounts and agricultural land use data (RVO, 2024). This integration allows to assess how the current state and recent changes of WLF differ between agricultural land and other types of land use in rural areas. Based on these analyses, we provide recommendations for the monitoring of the Dutch landscape plan targets and the use of the Dutch EA completed with LiDAR data to monitor WLF.

2. Methods

2.1. Case study areas

We carried out our study in three Dutch case study areas (Fig. 1): the province of Zeeland in the South West, the Rivierenland region in the center of the country, and the province of Limburg in the South East. The three case study areas cover four main types of landscape (Raap et al., 2022):

- (i) The South Western marine clay landscape, which covers most of Zeeland. It is an open landscape with a characteristic polder structure.
- (ii) The southern cover sand landscape is a slightly undulating landscape crossed by rivers. It covers a large part of Limburg and a minor part of Rivierenland. Characteristic WLF are forest patches.
- (iii) The river landscape is an open landscape with a characteristic structure of river floodplains, river banks, dikes and swamp soils. It covers most of the Rivierenland region along the Rhine river, and part of Limburg, along the Maas river. On river banks, plots are small and often used as orchards in Rivierenland. Willow coppices are characteristic WLF in this landscape.
- (iv) The Limburg south hilly landscape is a loess area with relatively large height differences. In valleys, plots are small and often surrounded by rows of trees or hedges. On slopes, characteristics features named *grachten*, hedges with steep edges, have been planted to counteract erosion.

Our study was focused on rural zones, thus excluded urban areas, nature areas (Natura 2000 and National Nature Network areas) and large infrastructures (e.g. motorways) (see 2.4.1). These rural zones consist of agricultural areas, i.e. parcels dedicated to agricultural production, but also house gardens, farmyards, small roads and canals and their verges, and fragmented (semi-) natural areas such as WLFs and

Fig. 1. Location of case study areas in the Netherlands.

natural grasslands. The national plan targets for WLF cover rural zones, but EU policies targets for WLFs only cover agricultural areas. Therefore, we further distinguished the state and trends of WLFs in agricultural areas from the state and trends of WLFs in other land uses within rural zones (see 2.6).

2.2. Overview of the methodological approach

Fig. 2 presents the overall methodological approach and main datasets used (see 2.3) to address our research questions. We developed an automated LiDAR data processing workflow (see 2.4) to assess the

Fig. 2. Overview of the methodological approach.

current extent and recent trends of WLF (RQ1). The current extent and recent trends of WLF based on EA data (RQ2) were quantified through processing of existing datasets (see 2.5). We compared the results of these two analyses (see 2.5) to assess differences between LiDAR-based results and EA data results (RQ3). Finally, we used LiDAR-based results to assess differences in WLF extent and recent trends between agricultural land and other land uses (RQ4, see 2.6).

2.3. Data sources

Table 1 provides an overview of each dataset, with full name and acronym, description of the main characteristics and how it was used in this study.

2.3.1. Ecosystem accounts and Top10NL data

The Dutch ecosystem extent accounts provide a time series of yearly (period 2013 – 2021) ecosystem extent maps (NL ET maps), as vector maps or raster maps of 2.5 m resolution, with 52 ecosystem type (ET) classes (Statistics Netherlands & WUR, 2022). For this study, we simplified the 52 ET classes into 8 aggregated ET categories (Table 2). Two of these categories correspond to WLF: forest (aggregation of forest ET classes), when located in rural landscapes, and hedgerows. Both forest and hedgerows ET classes in the NL ET maps were obtained from forest polygons of the Top10NL database (Kadaster, 2024). The Top10NL is an object-based topographic database, yearly updated through photointerpretation and digitalization of stereoscopic aerial photography (Beeldmateriaal Nederland, 2024). Top10NL forest polygons with a width smaller than 10 m. and a length higher than 100 m. were classified in the NL ET maps under the ET class “Hedges and tree lines”, distinct from other forest ET classes.

Besides forest polygons, the Top10NL database records narrow linear features covered by trees as polylines, which are classified as hedgerows or tree lines in the Top10NL database (see Table 3 for definition and recording criteria). These polylines are not included in the NL ET maps, but are included in a hedgerows density indicator in the ecosystem condition accounts. The Top10NL database also records isolated trees (as point data, see Table 3 for definition and recording criteria), but these are not included in any of the EA. In our analysis, we combined data on WLF from the NL ET maps with Top10NL polylines and points, and we compared this NL ET maps – Top10 NL data with LiDAR-based WLF maps.

2.3.2. LiDAR data

We used the Digital Terrain Model (DTM) and Digital Surface Model (DSM) at 50 cm resolution generated from airborne LiDAR data (Actueel Hoogtebestand Nederland – AHN – data, ahn.nl), acquired during the AHN2, AHN3 and AHN4 campaigns between 2011 and 2021 during winter (December to March). The point density ranged from 6 to 10 points per m² for AHN2 and AHN3, and from 10 to 14 points per m² for AHN4. For each 50 cm pixel, the DSM estimates average elevation (taking into account buildings, infrastructures and vegetation) while the DTM estimates ground level elevation. Because it takes several years to acquire airborne LiDAR data over the Netherlands (ahn.nl/kwaliteitsbesluit), our studied regions are covered by different acquisition years (Table 4).

2.3.3. Agricultural land use data

We used the 2024 version of the Dutch Land Parcel Information System (LPIS) data (RVO, 2024), which records all agricultural land parcels, with a distinction between parcels used for agricultural production and parcels declared as landscape features (classified as woody, water and other) by farmers. The LPIS data was used to (1) complete the map used to mask forest polygons located outside rural zones (see 2.4.1.) and (2) for the assessment to detect WLF current state and trends in agricultural areas within rural areas (see 2.6).

Table 1
Overview of all datasets used in the study.

Acronym	Full name	Description	Use in the study
NL ET map	Netherlands SFEA EA ecosystem extent maps 2013–2021	Vector maps or raster maps of 2.5 m resolution, with 52 ecosystem type (ET) classes, wall to wall national coverage of the Netherlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Forest” ET located in rural areas: Comparison of WLF state and trend between the NL ET map + Top10NL data and LiDAR based WLF maps ET “Business park”, “Mining, land fill, etc. . .”, “Sport park” and “Residential recreation”: Input data to the rural areas mask Assessment of LiDAR-based WLF state and trends in non-agricultural areas within rural areas Linear objects hedgerows and tree lines, tree points: Comparison of WLF state and trend between the NL ET map + Top10NL data and LiDAR based WLF maps Powerlines and windmills objects: masking of powerlines and windmills in the LiDAR derived CHM
Top10NL	Netherlands national topographic database	Object-based topographic database (scale 1:5000 to 1:25000)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building polygons: masking of buildings in the LiDAR-derived CHM Basis map for the delineation of the rural areas mask Input data to the rural areas mask Assessment of LiDAR-based WLF state and trends in agricultural areas within rural areas
BAG LG map LPIS	Basisregistratie Adressen en Gebouwen Landelijk Gebied kaart Agrarisch Areeal Nederland	Object-based database of buildings Vector map of agricultural parcels boundaries	Production of LiDAR based WLF maps
LiDAR	Airborne LiDAR data	DTM and DSM at 50 cm resolution generated from airborne LiDAR data (Actueel Hoogtebestand Nederland – AHN – data, ahn.nl)	Validation of LiDAR-based WLF types maps and change maps
Aerial photography	Aerial photographic images, covering the whole area of Netherlands every year (Beeldmateriaal Nederland, 2024)	RGB ortho photographic images from 2006 (50 cm resolution), 2011 (25 cm resolution), 2021 & 2023 (7.5 cm resolution), color-infrared images from 2013 (25 cm resolution)	

Table 2
Aggregation of NL ET maps ET classes into ET categories.

ET category	ET classes
Agriculture	Cropland, regular; Cropland, extensive; Pasture, permanent; Pasture, temporal; Pasture, extensive; Greenhouse horticulture; Nursery container fields; Fallow land; Arable field margins; Other, agricultural grassland; Perennials, regular; Perennials, extensive.
Built-up/ infrastructure	Built-up (urban); Built-up (rural); Business park; Mining, land fills, etc.; Infrastructural; Marine, other; Sport park; Residential recreation; other; Other terrain
Public green space	Landscape garden; Public park (large); Public park (small); Public green space, Semi-public green space.
Forest	(Semi-)natural forest; Plantation forest; Other forest; Swamp forest.
Hedgerows	Hedges and tree lines
Open nature	Tall herbs; Heathland; Drift sand; Semi-natural grassland; Biodiverse cropland; River floodplain; Other, nature grassland
Water & wetlands Coastal & marine	Bogs; Fens; Streams and rivers; Lakes; Brackish; Coastal dunes; Salt marshes; Beach; Intertidal and mud flats; Shoals; Estuarium; North sea; Wadden sea;

Table 3
Definition and recording criteria of Top10NL linear and point WLF.

Hedgerows (linear features)	1) rows of trees, either alone or in combination with shrubs, in which the distance between trees or the undergrowth obstructs the view up to at least human height, with a maximum planting width between trunks of 3 m; or 2) a row of shrubs planted next to each other (privet, hawthorn, conifers, hornbeam, etc.) that are trimmed at set times. Top10NL hedgerows have a minimum height of 1 m and minimum length of 100 m. Hedgerows within built-up areas and on farmyards are not recorded (unless a farmyard hedgerow continues beyond the yard). Hedgerows located on earthen walls (<i>houtwal</i> in Dutch) are recorded as forest polygons and not linear features.
Tree lines (linear features)	A number of trees (minimum 3) that stand in a row, where the distance between the trees is such that the line of trees does not form a visual obstruction up to human height. Top10NL tree lines have a minimum length of 100 m. A line of trees on or around a yard may be indicated if it continues into the adjacent or surrounding terrain.
Isolated trees (point features)	A woody plant with a single, sturdy, woody, and persistent trunk that branches at a certain height above the ground. Trees within built-up areas, on or along a street, in a garden, or on a farmyard are not included. A small number of trees standing close together are counted as one tree.

Table 4
AHN data acquisition dates and number of tiles per region.

Region	AHN data – acquisition years (source: https://www.ahn.nl/kwaliteitsbeschrijving)	Number of tiles
Zeeland	2014 (AHN3), 2020 (AHN4)	113
Limburg	2012 (AHN2), 2018 (AHN3), 2021 (AHN4)	112
Rivierenland	2011 (AHN2), 2015 (AHN3), 2021 (AHN4)	76

2.4. Current state and recent changes of WLF with LiDAR data

2.4.1. Current state of WLF with LiDAR data

We assessed the current state of WLF based on LiDAR data. The LiDAR AHN data is available for download as 5x6.5 km tiles in public repositories. For each tile covering our regions of interest, the DSM and DTM files were downloaded and processed according to the processing chain described in Fig. A1. First, we generated a canopy height model (CHM) by subtracting DTM pixel heights from DSM pixel heights. Values exceeding the maximum height of trees in the Netherlands (set at > 50 m) and negative values were reclassified as NA. Then, the CHM was

smoothed with the mean of a 3x3 pixels (1.5 x 1.5 m) moving window to fill empty pixels (function focal of the R terra package, v.1.8.21, Hijmans et al. (2024)). Next, we used the BAG dataset (Kadaster, 2023) to mask buildings and the Top10NL dataset (Kadaster, 2024) to mask powerlines and windmills in the smoothed CHM. Smoothing was done before masking to avoid that pixels overlapping with the edge of masked polygons are filled with a value during the smoothing step.

Next, individual tree tops detection was performed using a local maximum filter with variable windows size (`locate_trees` algorithm of the R `lidR` package, v.4.1.1, Roussel et al. (2020)). Then, the final CHM and detected individual tree tops were combined to segment individual trees using the method from Silva et al. (2016) implemented in the R `lidR` package. This step generated a raster map (0.5 m resolution) with delineated tree crowns. This tree crowns map was resampled to 1 m resolution to reduce processing time in the next steps. After resampling, adjacent tree crowns were aggregated in patches using the `patches` function in the R terra package (Hijmans et al., 2024), to produce a tree crowns patches map.

Next, we classified this tree crowns patches map in a WLF map. We used a minimum bounding rectangle to estimate the length of each patch and deducted the patch width by dividing the patch area by its length. We removed very small patches (area below 12.57 m², corresponding to the area of a tree with a 4 m diameter crown) and classified the remaining patches under three types of WLF: (1) isolated trees/groups of trees, (2) forest patches and (3) hedgerows. The classification was based on the size and length – width ratio of patches, following the decision tree presented in Fig. 3.

To focus our assessment on rural zones, we masked tree crowns located in urban and nature areas, using the *Landelijk Gebied* (LG) map produced by Roelofsens (2022), which delineates rural zones, with some modifications. First, we excluded from the LG map the areas classified as “Business park”, “Mining, land fill, etc...”, “Sport park” and “Residential recreation” in the 2021 ET map, so that tree crowns located in these land use classes are excluded and confusions with non vegetation vertical structures are avoided (e.g. cranes in mining, land fill areas). Second, we updated the agricultural areas of the LG map using the most recent LPIS data (see 2.2.3). A sample of the final mask is shown in Fig. 4. Note that the resulting rural zones still include built-up and infrastructure areas, mainly corresponding to house gardens, farm yards, roads and canal verges. The resulting rural zones also include fragments of nature areas, including forest patches and hedgerows, located next to fields, in farmyards and on roads and canals verges.

Urban and nature areas masking was carried out after classifying WLFs to avoid classification artefacts on (non-masked) edges of masked forest patches. These non-masked edges have a linear shape and would have been classified as hedgerows instead of forest patches if the WLF classification had taken place after masking.

Using this LiDAR-based WLF map produced in each region, we calculated the area of each WLF category (forest patches, isolated/groups of trees, hedgerows) for the year 2021 in Limburg and Rivierenland, and 2020 in Zeeland.

2.4.2. Quality control of LiDAR-based WLF maps

The quality of WLF maps was checked visually, using the CHM and aerial photography for comparison. Moreover, we compared the most recent WLF maps (2021 in Limburg and Rivierenland, 2020 in Zeeland) to a reference sample of WLFs visually identified on aerial photography in each region. To collect the reference sample, we randomly selected 30 forest polygons, 30 tree lines, 30 hedgerows and 30 trees from the Top10NL data in each region. We identified these reference WLFs on aerial photography and assessed by manual delineation how well the reference WLFs were covered by our LiDAR-based WLF maps. We recorded the percentage of the reference WLF covered by the LiDAR-based WLF map, and under which WLF categories (forest patches, isolated/groups of trees, hedgerows) the reference WLF were classified in the LiDAR-based WLF map. We used as references the area covered by

Fig. 3. Decision tree for the classification of tree crown patches in types of WLF.

Fig. 4. Sample of mask (red shaded) used to select rural areas and exclude urban and nature areas, in Limburg, around the city of Weert. All red shaded areas are considered rural areas and are used to assess WLFs. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

tree canopies on the aerial photography for patchy features (forest polygons and trees) and the length covered by tree canopies on the aerial photography for line features (tree lines and hedgerows). In parallel, we recorded the width of the reference trees lines and hedgerows (width of tree canopies on the aerial photography), and the area of the reference trees, which we used to estimate the total area of Top10NL features (see 2.5).

2.4.3. Recent changes of WLF based on LiDAR data

2.4.3.1. Net changes. The WLF mapping workflow (see 2.4.1) was repeated for each region and acquisition year to calculate changes in WLF area for the years 2012–2018–2021 in Limburg, 2011–2015–2021 in Rivierenland, and 2014–2020 in Zeeland.

2.4.3.2. Gross changes. WLF maps of the first and last LiDAR acquisition years were subtracted to produce WLF change maps (pixels classified as loss, gain and no change) for the periods 2012–2021 in Limburg, 2011–2021 in Rivierenland and 2014–2020 in Zeeland. Using these change maps, we calculated gains and losses of WLF area during these periods. All WLF types (forest patch, hedgerows, trees) were aggregated in the WLF maps used to produce these change maps. Thus, no distinction between WLF types was made at the subsequent steps of validation and analysis of the types of changes (see below).

2.4.3.3. Validation. We validated the change maps using aerial

photography as reference data. We aggregated WLF change pixels in gained and lost patches (patches function in the R package terra) and calculated the area of these change patches. We categorized change patches per size in order to get samples of change patches potentially representing different types of change (e.g. trimming vs. clear-cutting): less than 12.57 m² (about the size of a tree crown), between 12.57 m² and 100 m², between 100 m² and 200 m², between 200 m² and 1000 m², between 1000 m² and 1 ha, more than 1 ha. We randomly selected 467 change patches spanning the range of change patches size categories (see Table 5) and visually checked the nature of changes using aerial photographic images, covering the whole area of Netherlands every year (Beeldmateriaal Nederland, 2024). We classified change patches as false or true changes by visually comparing change patches to aerial photography before the first date (2006, 2011 and 2013) and after the last date (2021 and 2023) of the change map period. Change patches were labelled as true if the change patch actually corresponded to a gain or loss of tree vegetation confirmed by aerial photography comparison, and as false on the contrary.

We used the results of the validation to adjust the estimated net change area taking into account classification errors in the change maps. We calculated \hat{p}_i , the proportion of correctly classified change patches in the validation sample, for each category i of change patch size. We excluded gain/loss patches from size categories with a \hat{p}_i less than 0.8. This led to excluding all changes with a size less than 100 m² when calculating the adjusted net change area. For the remaining change size categories, we calculated the total areas of gain/loss by summing areas of all gain/loss patches from the WLF change maps in the size category. Then we multiplied these map-based sums by the percentage of correct change detection in the relevant size category. Thereby, we obtained adjusted gain and loss areas (Eq.1), with a 95 % confidence interval estimated with the normal approximation method (Eq. (2)).

$$Adjusted\ Gain/Loss\ Area_i = Map\ Gain/Loss\ Area_i \cdot \hat{p}_i \quad \mp \Delta\ Adjusted\ Gain/Loss\ Area_i \quad (1)$$

Table 5
Number of change patches compared to reference data in each region per size category (e.g. in Limburg, we compared to reference data 10 gain patches and 10 loss patches of a size less than 12.57 m²).

Category of change patches size	Limburg		Rivierenland		Zeeland		Total	
	Gain	Loss	Gain	Loss	Gain	Loss	Gain	Loss
Less than 12.57 m ²	10	10	10	10	10	10	30	30
12.57 to 100 m ²	19	18	20	18	19	19	58	55
100 to 200 m ²	10	10	10	10	10	10	30	30
200 to 1000 m ²	20	20	20	20	20	20	60	60
1000 m ² to 1 ha	10	10	10	10	10	10	30	30
More than 1 ha	10	10	10	10	4	10	24	30
Total	79	78	80	78	73	79	232	235

$$\Delta \text{ Adjusted Gain/Loss Area}_i = \text{Map Gain/Loss Area}_i \cdot 1.9599 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\hat{p}_i(1 - \hat{p}_i)}{n_i}} \quad (2)$$

Where,

Map Gain/Loss Area_i is the sum of gain/loss patches area in gain/loss map for patches of size category i,

p_i is the proportion of correct changes in gain/loss patches sample in size category i,

n_i is the number of gain/loss patches compared to reference data in size category i.

Finally, we summed the adjusted gains and losses areas to obtain the adjusted net change area (Eq. (3), with a 95 % confidence interval taking into account the propagation of uncertainties of adjusted gain and loss areas (Eq. (4).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Adjusted Net Change Area} &= \sum_{i=1}^4 (\text{Adjusted Gain Area}_i \\ &\quad - \text{Adjusted Loss Area}_i) \\ &\pm \Delta \text{ Adjusted Net Change Area} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta \text{ Adjusted Net Change Area} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^4 \Delta \text{ Adjusted Gain Area}_i^2 + \Delta \text{ Adjusted Loss Area}_i^2} \quad (4)$$

Where,

i is the change size category,

Adjusted Gain/Loss Area_i is the output of Eq. (1) for the change size category i,

Δ Adjusted Gain/Loss Area_i is the output of Eq. (2) for the change size category i.

2.4.3.4. Types of changes. In addition to the validation of changes, we used aerial photography to identify the types of changes and obtain insights into the nature and cause of WLF changes. We labelled each change patch as new or clear cut features, part of a coppice regrowth or cutting, canopy cover loss (gaps, trimming) or growth. We also noted whether the observed changes corresponded to a change in land use, and the location of the changed WLF (e.g. in farmyard or on field border).

2.5. Current state and recent changes of WLF with NL ET maps and Top10NL data

To compare results obtained from LiDAR data to the data available in the EA, we assessed WLF recorded in the NL ET maps and Top10NL features. We calculated the area of forest and hedgerows ET categories in the NL ET maps. We calculated the length of Top10NL line features (hedgerows and tree lines) and the number of Top10NL points (trees). To convert linear features length and number of trees to area, we estimated the average width of Top10NL linear features and average area of Top10NL trees on a sample of 60 linear features and 30 trees in each region (see 2.4.2). To be consistent with the LiDAR data, we used the same years (2021 in Limburg and Rivierenland, 2020 in Zeeland) and same masks (see 2.4.1 and Fig. 4) to exclude buildings, areas under powerlines, windmills and non-rural areas from the NL ET maps and Top10NL features. We repeated this assessment for each year of the 2013–2021 time series. Finally, to understand differences of WLF

assessment between the LiDAR based maps and the NL ET maps, we calculated the area of LiDAR WLF located within each ET category of the NL ET maps of 2021 (in Limburg and Rivierenland) and 2020 (in Zeeland).

2.6. State and trends of WLF in agricultural and other land use

To determine the state of WLF in agricultural land within rural zones, we calculated the area of LiDAR WLF located within the LPIS parcels at the last LiDAR acquisition years in each region. To assess trends of WLF in agricultural land within rural zones, we calculated the area of WLF changes (gains and losses of WLF) within the LPIS parcels, using the LiDAR based WLF change maps excluding small size changes (see 2.4.3). We distinguished between LPIS parcels dedicated to production, parcels declared as WLF, and parcels declared as other types of landscape features.

To determine the state of WLF in non-agricultural land within rural zones, we used the NL ET maps. After excluding the agricultural land, we calculated the area of LiDAR based WLF located within each ET category at the last LiDAR acquisition years in each region. To assess trends of WLF on non-agricultural land within rural zones, we calculated the area of WLF gains and losses located in rural zones (excluding agricultural land), using the LiDAR based WLF change maps (excluding small size changes, see 2.4.3).

3. Results

3.1. Quality of WLF maps derived from LiDAR data

Visual control showed a good agreement between our WLF maps

Fig. 5. Extract of LiDAR-based WLF map in the Rivierenland region. Top: Aerial photography, 2021; Bottom: LiDAR-based WLF 2021 map features overlaid on aerial photography (CRS: EPSG:28992 – Amersfoort / RD New).

Fig. 6. Incorrect classification of trainlines power poles as hedgerows in LiDAR-based WLF 2021 map, overlaid on aerial photography 2021 (CRS: EPSG:28992 – Amersfoort / RD New).

Table 6

Comparison of WLF maps (2020 in Zeeland, 2021 in Limburg and Rivierenland) with reference aerial photography.

Top10NL feature	Average size		WLF cover* detected by LiDAR-based WLF maps (%)			
	Qty	Unit	(group of) Trees	Hedgerow	Forest Patch	Any WLF type
Forest polygons	2229	m ²	1.7	1.6	82.5	85.8
Tree lines	7.3	m	19.3	8.4	68.0	95.8
Hedgerows	4.6	m	6.0	28.3	15.5	49.8
Trees	85	m ²	34.6	3.4	54.7	92.7

* % presented in this table correspond to the WLF cover detection % area-weighted average (forest polygons and trees) or length-weighted average (tree lines and hedgerows) of reference features.

derived from LiDAR data and GoogleEarth images, with most of WLF in the landscape being captured in our maps (Fig. 5). A few not masked vertical infrastructure elements, such as train lines power poles (Fig. 6),

were misclassified as WLF.

Comparison of LiDAR-based WLF maps with the reference WLF on aerial photography showed that the LiDAR based maps detected 85.8 % of the forest polygons, 95.8 % of the tree lines and 92.7 % of trees, but only 49.8 % of hedgerows (see Table 6 and Table A1 in appendix for detailed results per region). The low detection of hedgerows was due to the failure of the LiDAR based map to detect low hedgerows with a narrow (less than 2 m) width (see Fig. 7).

There was a good agreement between the Top10NL WLF classification and the LiDAR-based WLF types classification (see Table7) in the case of forest polygons: 96.1 % of the reference forest polygons were classified as forest patches in the LiDAR-based maps. That was not the case for the other types of WLF. Top10NL tree lines and trees were more classified in the LiDAR-based maps as forest patches, respectively 71 % and 59 %, than as trees, respectively 20.2 % and 37.3 %. Top10NL hedgerows were mostly classified as hedgerows in the LiDAR-based maps (56.8 %), but also as forest patches (31.1 %) and trees (12.1 %).

3.2. Current state and recent trends of WLF in rural landscapes based on LiDAR data

The three regions differed in their density of WLF, with Zeeland having a relatively low density (2.4 % of the total rural area in 2020), Limburg a relatively high density (8.2 % of the total rural area in 2021), and Rivierenland being in between (4.8 % of the total rural area in 2021), according to LiDAR based estimates (Table 8).

According to WLF LiDAR maps, the WLF area increased by 0.2 % per year between 2012 and 2021 in Limburg, was stable between 2011 and

Table 7

Agreement (%) between the WLF types classification of the Top10NL data and the LiDAR-based WLF maps.

Top10NL feature classification	WLF cover classified by LiDAR-based WLF maps (%)		
	(group of) Trees	Hedgerow	Forest Patch
Forest polygons	2.0	1.8	96.1
Tree lines	20.2	8.8	71.0
Hedgerows	12.1	56.78	31.1
Trees	37.3	3.7	59.0

Fig. 7. Several Top10NL hedgerows, corresponding to low and narrow features, are not detected by the LiDAR-based WLF map. Left: Aerial photography 2021; Middle: Top10NL linear features overlaid on aerial photography; Right: LiDAR-based WLF 2021 map and Top10NL linear features overlaid on aerial photography (CRS: EPSG:28992 – Amersfoort / RD New).

Table 8

LiDAR based WLF area (in ha) and WLF cover (%) in rural areas, agricultural land, and rural areas outside agricultural land in the three regions (last LiDAR acquisition date).

	Rural area – in agricultural land			Rural area – outside agricultural land			Rural area – total		
	Area WLF (in ha)	Total area (in ha)	% WLF cover	Area WLF (in ha)	Total area (in ha)	% WLF cover	Area WLF (in ha)	Total area (in ha)	% WLF cover
Limburg (for 2021)	6,247	112,272	5.6 %	4,919	24,691	19.9 %	11,166	136,963	8.2 %
Rivierenland (for 2021)	2,283	84,213	2.7 %	2,561	17,161	14.9 %	4,844	101,374	4.8 %
Zeeland (for 2020)	1,546	128,797	1.2 %	2,001	16,933	11.8 %	3,547	145,730	2.4 %
All three regions	10,076	325,282	3.1 %	9,481	58,786	16.1 %	19,557	384,067	5.1 %

Fig. 8. Adjusted total gain, loss and net change WLF areas in hectare in Limburg (2012–2021), Rivierenland (2011–2021) and Zeeland (2014–2020), according to Lidar data adjusted for false change detections. Error bars show 95% confidence intervals.

2012 in Rivierenland, and increased by 0.8 % per year between 2014 and 2020 in Zeeland. However, the comparison of change patches with aerial photography revealed that most changes of small size (< 100 m²) were false changes. When these small size patches are excluded and areas of change are adjusted for false detections (see 2.4.3 and Tables A2, A3 and A4 in Appendix), the WLF area actually declined in all regions (Fig. 8). In Limburg, the WLF area decreased by 0.35 ± 0.12 % per year (349 ± 120 ha); in Rivierenland, the WLF area decreased by 0.95 ± 0.08 % per year (440 ± 40 ha); and in Zeeland, the WLF area decreased by 1.2 ± 0.15 % per year (248 ± 31 ha).

In the sample of change patches checked with aerial photography, 66 % of the new WLF area corresponded to new features and 34 % to growth of existing features (canopy growth or regrowth of a coppice). A minor part (about 32 %) of new WLF were due to a land use change, which consisted mostly of agricultural land converted to a forest patch. 74 % of the lost WLF area corresponded to clear cut features and 26 % to loss of canopy cover in existing features (gaps in canopy, trimming or coppice cut). Most clear cut WLF (about 90 %) were due to a land use change, which consisted mostly of the conversion of forest patches or hedgerows to agricultural land (55 %), but also to semi-natural grassland (25 %) and other land uses (e.g. road infrastructure). Overall, 87 % of net changes of WLF area resulted from new/clear cut WLF, and 13 %

from growth/canopy losses in existing features.

3.3. Current state and recent trends of WLF in rural landscapes based on NL ET map and Top10NL data

The WLF area estimated from the NL ET maps and Top10NL data was lower than the WLF area estimated from the LiDAR data, by 14 %, 5 % and 29 % in Limburg, Rivierenland and Zeeland respectively (Table 9). On average, NL ET map – Top10NL data captured 85.4 % of the LiDAR based WLF area: 51.8 % was captured by the NL ET maps and 33.6 % by the Top10NL linear and point features.

Similarly to the LiDAR based trends, the area of forest and hedgerows ET in the NL ET maps decreased in all regions, by 0.8 % per year in Zeeland (2014–2020), 0.4 % per year in Rivierenland (2013–2021) and 0.7 % per year in Limburg (2013–2021) (Fig. 9). The area of Top10NL features, i.e. hedgerows, tree lines and trees, showed a large increase in all regions, but this was likely due to an incomplete registration of these features before 2015.

3.4. Differences between LiDAR-based and NL ET maps – Top10NL data

LiDAR-based WLF maps did not cover 30 to 40 % (depending on the

Table 9

Comparison of the WLF area in ET map – Top10NL data to the LiDAR-based WLF area (in 2021 in Limburg and Rivierenland, 2020 in Zeeland).

	WLF area in NL ET map – Top10NL (in ha)	WLF area in LiDAR-based WLF maps (in ha)	Ratio WLF area in NL ET map – Top10NL over WLF area in LiDAR-based maps	Difference WLF area in NL ET map – Top10NL – LiDAR-based WLF maps (in ha)
Limburg				
ET map WLF (forest and hedgerow ET)	5,961	4,168	1.43	1,793
Top10NL linear and point WLF	3,641	6,998	0.52	– 3,357
All WLF Rivierenland	9,602	11,166	0.86	– 1,564
ET map WLF (forest and hedgerow ET)	2,768	1,601	1.72	1,167
Top10NL linear and point WLF	1,816	3,243	0.56	– 1,427
All WLF Zeeland	4,584	4,844	0.95	– 260
ET map WLF (forest and hedgerow ET)	1,394	937	1.48	457
Top10NL linear and point WLF	1,119	2,610	0.43	– 1,491
All WLF All three regions	2,513	3,547	0.71	– 1,034
ET map WLF (forest and hedgerow ET)	10,123	6,706	1.51	3,417
Top10NL linear and point WLF	6,576	12,851	0.51	– 6,275
All WLF	16,699	19,557	0.85	– 2,858

region) of the forest and hedgerow ETs area in the NL ET map, a total of 3,417 ha considering the three regions together (See Fig. 10). This uncomplete coverage was in part due to uncomplete tree canopy detection (see 3.1), but also because forest and hedgerow ETs include areas of bare soil and low vegetation (see Fig. 11). Conversely LiDAR-based WLF maps detected 1.8 to 2.3 times more WLF area, a total of 6,275 ha considering the three regions together, than the Top10NL data (Table 9). These WLF were especially located in built-up & infrastructure and agriculture ET (Fig. 10). The built-up & infrastructure areas containing WLFs correspond to houses, farm yards, road and canal verges located in rural areas, which were not masked as urban areas (see 2.4.1). The total area of LiDAR-derived WLF located in built-up & infrastructure ET was 5,071 ha considering the three regions together, with 2,268 ha covering large roads and infrastructures (see Fig. 12).

3.5. State and trends of WLF in agricultural and other land use

The agricultural land included 43 %, 47 % and 56 % of the LiDAR-based WLF area in Zeeland, Rivierenland and Limburg respectively. The rest of the WLF area was located in surrounding areas, such as farmyards, built-up zones, roads and canal verges. WLF covered 16.1 % of the surrounding areas (11.8 % in Zeeland, 14.9 % in Rivierenland and 19.9 % in Limburg) but only 3.1 % of the agricultural land (1.2 % in Zeeland, 2.7 % in Rivierenland and 5.6 % in Limburg) (Table 5).

LiDAR WLF detected in agricultural land coincided largely with WLF

parcels reported by farmers (in LPIS data, see 2.2.3), but were also found in agricultural parcels, likely consisting of isolated trees, and other types of landscape features (Figs. 13 and 15). LiDAR WLFs did not cover 35 % of the area of WLF parcels reported by farmers, 2,508 ha in total. When this area was added to the LiDAR-based WLF area, the percentage of agricultural land covered by WLFs reached 1.4 % in Zeeland, 3.4 % in Rivierenland and 7 % in Limburg (3.9 % for the three regions together).

WLF detected in surrounding areas coincided with the forest and hedgerows ET, but were also largely located in built-up & infrastructure, public green space and open nature ETs (Figs. 14 and 16).

WLF trends were all declining in agricultural land and surrounding areas in the three regions. However, in Limburg, the decline was relatively less large in agricultural land (–0.4 % per year) than in surrounding areas (–0.5 % per year), while the decline was relatively larger in agricultural land than in surrounding areas in Zeeland (–1.6 % per year in agricultural land, –0.8 % per year in surrounding areas) and Rivierenland (–1% per year in agricultural land, –0.7 % per year in surrounding areas).

4. Discussion

In this study, we used LiDAR data to generate new maps of WLF, allowing us to assess the current state and recent trends of WLF in three regions of the Netherlands, and compare these results with existing data in the NL ET maps and Top10NL database. Information about the current state and insights how to analyze trends in WLF is crucial since several major national and European policy programs have set targets around landscape features (e.g. the Dutch landscape plan, the CAP and the European Nature Restoration Law).

Our LiDAR estimates of WLF area were larger than the WLF area estimated from the ET map – Top10NL data (Table 9). This difference was mainly due to the area of LiDAR-based WLFs that overlaps with the built-up & infrastructure, public green space and agriculture ET (Fig. 10). These ecosystem types are primarily delineated based on land use (Statistics Netherlands & WUR, 2022), which may correspond to different land covers. Thus, forest patches, hedgerows and trees located in house gardens, public parks, farmyards or fields are not counted as forest or hedgerows ET in the NL ET maps. The same holds true for WLF located in open nature ecosystems, which may include scattered features of woody vegetation. Those WLF that are not located in forest and hedgerow ET of the NL ET map may yet be registered in the Top10NL database. However, the Top10NL data is incomplete (van Doorn et al., 2016), among others limited by minimum recording criteria. For instance, WLF in farmyards are not recorded, nor hedgerows with a length smaller than 100 m (Kadaster, 2020; Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed et al., 2024). Taking the three regions together, our results suggest that around 15 % of the WLF area is missing in the ET map – Top10NL data.

It should be noted that our LiDAR method estimated the area of the WLF based on the extent of their tree canopies. On the one hand, this method leads to an underestimation of the WLF area, since WLF often consist of a mix of trees, shrubs and grasses without a complete ground coverage by woody vegetation (see Fig. 11): a total of 3,417 ha of forest and hedgerows ET were not mapped as WLF in the LiDAR maps (see 3.4). On the other hand, this method leads to an overestimation of the WLF in built-up & infrastructure ET, when WLF are located next to, with their canopies overlapping, paved surfaces (see Fig. 12). The total area of LiDAR WLF located in built-up and infrastructure ET was 5,071 ha, with 2,268 ha located in large roads and infrastructures (see 3.4). Overall, we estimate that underestimated and overestimated areas are similar. Eventually, low and narrow linear WLF were not completely detected by our method (Fig. 7), but the area covered by these features is small.

In this study, we also intended to map different types of WLF with LiDAR data based on their dimension and shape and, in particular, to distinguish hedgerows from forest patches. However, there was a poor agreement between the LiDAR-based WLF types classification and the

Fig. 9. Net changes of WLF area estimated with ET maps – Top10 NL data for the three case study areas.

Fig. 10. Repartition of the area of WLF (from most recent LiDAR data) per category of ET (NL ET map of 2021 for Limburg and Rivierenland, 2020 for Zeeland). Number labels inside bars correspond to the area, in hectares, of the ET category covered by WLF (green color) or not (brown color). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 11. Uncomplete coverage of a ET map forest patch by the LiDAR based WLF map (aerial photography 2021, CRS: EPSG:28992 – Amersfoort / RD New).

Fig. 12. Example of LiDAR based WLF partly covering a road (aerial photography 2021, CRS: EPSG:28992 – Amersfoort / RD New).

Top10 NL WLF classification (Table 7): 43 % of Top10NL hedgerows were classified as trees or forest patches by the LiDAR-based WLF maps in our validation sample. Top10NL hedgerows may have been partly classified as several trees and small forest patches rather than a single linear feature because of gaps in their canopy. Moreover, the minimum bounding rectangle method to determine patches dimensions worked well for patches with rectangular shapes but did not for patches with complex, sinuous shapes, which may have been recorded as forest patches rather than hedgerows. Therefore, using LiDAR data to map different types of WLF with accuracy requires further development.

According to our LiDAR based estimates, the three regions differed in their density of WLF, with Zeeland having a relatively low density (2.4 % of the rural area in 2020), Limburg a relatively high density (8.2 % of the rural area in 2020), and Rivierenland being in between (4.8 % of the rural area in 2021). Taken together, these three regions had on average a WLF coverage of 5.1 %. Extrapolating from a sample of rural landscapes with complete records of WLFs, van Doorn et al. (2016) estimated the total area of WLF to 117.000 ha, corresponding to a 3.5 % coverage of the rural areas in the Netherlands. However, this percentage was based on a total rural area of about 3.3 million ha, a figure about 1.5 times larger than estimated by Statistics Netherlands (2017) and a recent assessment by Roelofsen (2022). Recalculating the estimates of Van Doorn et al. (2016) with a total rural area of about 2.2 million ha, the percentage coverage found by van Doorn et al. (2016) gets close to our LiDAR based estimate, i.e. of 5.1 %.

The analysis of WLF trends based on LiDAR data indicated a decrease of the WLF area in the three regions: 0.35 ± 0.12 % per year (2012–2021) in Limburg, 0.95 ± 0.08 % per year (2011–2021) in Rivierenland and 1.2 ± 0.15 % per year (2014–2020) in Zeeland. The analysis of a sample of change patches with aerial photography showed that a large part (87 %) of net changes resulted from the new and clear cut WLF. Thus, our results indicate that the loss of WLF continues in the three studied regions. However, in the 34 % of WLF losses that were not associated to a land use change, it is possible that WLF were replanted in the following years. Moreover, 25 % of WLF losses associated to land use change corresponded to a conversion of WLF to semi-natural grasslands, which could be beneficial for biodiversity and ESs when the converted WLF does not have a high biodiversity value (e.g. a monospecific coppice). LiDAR based trends in agricultural land and non-agricultural land were both negative. The decline was relatively higher in agricultural area than in non-agricultural areas of Rivierenland and Zeeland. Similarly to LiDAR maps, the WLF area based on the ET maps decreased in all regions, mainly due to the decrease of the forest ET area. The area of Top10NL WLF increased but these changes may correspond to improvement in the completeness of the database rather than the recording of actual new features (Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed et al., 2024).

The national landscape plan (Hagendoorn et al., 2021) aims to have 10 % of the rural area covered by landscape features – 5 % with WLF and 5 % with blue landscape features (ponds, ditches) – both in the agricultural area and areas not dedicated to agriculture (farmyard and other land estates, areas along roads and canals, other public spaces). According to our LiDAR based results, the 5 % target for WLF is likely to be already achieved taking rural areas as a whole. In particular on non-agricultural land, the plan target seems largely achieved in each region and on average in the three regions taken together (16.1 %). However, this is not the case when one looks at agricultural land only, where the WLF density was 3.1 % for the three regions together (3.9 % when including bare/grassy parts of WLF not detected by LiDAR, see 3.5). Moreover, our LiDAR results indicate that the area of WLF continues to decrease on agricultural land. It is therefore uncertain whether the targets will be achieved, especially on agricultural land. Policy measures in the new implementation period of the CAP (2023–2027) could help to change WLF trends in agricultural land in the future. The Dutch National Strategic Plan for the CAP (van Landbouw et al., 2022) contains several measures which aim to enhance and maintain landscape features in

Fig. 13. Repartition of the area of WLF (from LiDAR data) per category of agricultural land (LPIS) within the rural areas. Number labels inside bars correspond to the area, in hectares, of the agricultural land category covered by WLF (green color) or not (brown color). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 14. Repartition of the area of WLF (from LiDAR data) per category of ecosystem type (NL ET map) in the rural areas, excluding agricultural land. Number labels inside bars correspond to the area, in hectares, of the ET category covered by WLF (green color) or not (brown color). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 15. WLF detected by LiDAR on a farmyard (aerial photography 2021, CRS: EPSG:28992 – Amersfoort / RD New).

Fig. 16. WLF detected by LiDAR on agricultural land and not registered in LPIS (aerial photography 2021, CRS: EPSG:28992 – Amersfoort / RD New).

agricultural land. First, parcels covered by landscape features are now eligible to direct payments, which was not the case before. Besides, farmers receiving CAP payments must (1) allocate a minimum share of 4 % agricultural area to non-productive use and (2) conserve existing landscape features. Second, the planting and management of landscape features are subsidized by investment support, eco-schemes and agri-environmental measures. Enhancing the monitoring of WLF is crucial to be able to assess the effectiveness of these policy measures in the future.

Recent CAP policy changes will also help to improve the monitoring of WLF, since landscape features parcels eligible to CAP payments are now reported by farmers and registered in the BRP and LPIS datasets. Therefore, from 2023 thereon, it will be possible to include in NL ET maps all WLF registered in the BRP and LPIS data. Our study demonstrates how LiDAR based WLF maps can further enhance WLF monitoring in rural areas with EA. WLF on agricultural land that are still not included in the BRP and LPIS data, e.g. isolated trees or small group of trees, can be detected with LiDAR. This is also the case for WLF on land surrounding agriculture parcels, for instance farmyards and road or canal verges. This will give a more complete picture of the WLF in rural areas. In addition, WLF percentage cover based on LiDAR data could be included in condition accounts, as a condition indicator for these non-

forest ET classes. However, when determining temporal changes in the area of WLF, LiDAR data should be used with caution. Simply counting WLF pixels in the time series of WLF maps showed an increasing or stable trend in our three studied regions. After assessing the accuracy of changes detection and adjusting for false change detection, the estimated trend was actually negative. Therefore, as with other remote sensing data, it is essential to estimate maps accuracy and change areas uncertainty using a reference dataset such as aerial photography (Olofsson et al., 2014).

Our study demonstrates the potential and limitations of LiDAR data to map and monitor WLF in the Dutch context with a relatively simple processing workflow using DSM and DTM products. More advanced processing approaches using the point cloud (the raw data used for processing the DSM and DTM) may overcome some of the limitations identified in our study, such as difficulties in differentiating linear and patchy WLF (Lucas et al., 2019). For monitoring WLF changes, an alternative approach combining WLF baseline mapping with LiDAR and change monitoring with high temporal resolution Sentinel 1–2 satellite data (Luscombe et al., 2023) may improve differentiation of clear cutting from pruning and regrowth cycles. LiDAR data could also enhance WLF mapping and monitoring by EA in other EU member states. Non-commercial airborne LiDAR data is available in many EU member states (Kakoulaki et al., 2021), but, to our knowledge, studies on the use of LiDAR data to map and monitor WLF are limited to two other European countries (Estrada et al., 2017; Luscombe et al., 2023). Therefore, further work is needed to test WLF mapping and monitoring in other countries, as LiDAR potential and limitations are likely to depend on types of WLF and biophysical characteristics of farming landscapes across European regions.

In addition to the monitoring of WLF area and condition, our work has implications for the assessment of ESs provided by WLF. The spatial location of WLF in landscapes is a key factor driving their effects on farmland biodiversity and ESs. For instance, the effectiveness of WLF to support crop pollination is influenced by their distance to pollinator dependent crop fields (Albrecht et al., 2020) and the presence of other semi-natural habitats in the surrounding landscape (Garratt et al., 2017). Specific vegetation structure and composition of WLF also influences their capacity to deliver ESs (Kremen et al., 2018). Besides mapping WLF, LiDAR data can provide information on the vegetation structure of WLF, such as percentage of canopy cover or vegetation height, which is relevant to assess the potential of these features to provide habitats to farmland species (Broughton et al., 2021; Graham et al., 2018). Such vegetation structure indicators could be included in condition accounts, as a condition indicator for the forest and hedgerow ET classes. Improved data on the extent, location and condition of WLF based on LiDAR data could therefore improve the accuracy of ES modelling in EA, but further research is needed to test this hypothesis.

5. Conclusion

Our study shows that the net area of WLF in rural areas continued to decrease over 2011–2021 in the three studied regions, both in agricultural land and in surrounding other land uses (e.g. house gardens and farmyards, infrastructures). While the WLF density in these other land uses remains relatively high (16.1 %), the WLF density in agricultural land is only 3.9 %, well below the target of 5 % WLF cover by 2050 of the Dutch national landscape plan. In order to achieve the targets, the CAP and other national policies should strengthen measures that aim to maintain existing and establish new WLF. This will improve habitats to farmland biodiversity and enhance the provision of ESs.

EA complemented with LiDAR data could support the Dutch national landscape plan by monitoring the extent and condition of WLF. Should this policy application be pursued, the Dutch EA could be complemented with LiDAR data and other data sources to support the monitoring of WLFs. This could be done in the following way. First, WLFs registered by farmers in the BRP and LPIS data could be included in the NL ET maps.

Second, LiDAR data could be used to include WLFs that are not registered in the BRP and LPIS data in the NL ET maps. These WLFs may be located in agricultural land but also in farmyards and road or canal verges. Third, LiDAR data could also be used to monitor the vegetation structure of WLFs ETs in the NL ET maps. These two last indicators, i.e. the percentage cover by WLF in agricultural land and surrounding ETs, and tree vegetation structure metrics, could be recorded in the ecosystem condition accounts. When available at national scale with regular updates, LiDAR data could also enhance WLF monitoring by EA in other EU member states.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nicolas Grondard: Writing – original draft, Methodology,

Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. Lenny van Bussel: Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. Lars Hein: Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix: Additional figures and tables

Fig. A1. GIS workflow to generate WLF maps

Table A1

Comparison of WLF maps (2020 in Zeeland, 2021 in Limburg and Rivierenland) with reference aerial photography – detailed results per region.

Region	Top10NL feature	Average size		% of WLF cover* detected by LiDAR-based WLF maps as ...			
		Qty	Unit	(group of) trees (in %)	hedgerow (in %)	forest patch (in %)	any WLF type (in %)
Limburg	Forest polygons	2009	m ²	2.1	0.6	86.5	89.2
	Tree lines	10.2	m	12.9	4.4	80.4	97.8
	Hedgerows	5.4	m	5.4	17.0	16.5	38.9
	Trees	96	m ²	55.4	7.4	31.5	94.3
Rivierenland	Forest polygons	2021	m ²	1.9	1.6	81.8	85.2
	Tree lines	7.1	m	20.3	7.8	64.6	92.7
	Hedgerows	4.5	m	4.6	25.1	14.7	44.5

(continued on next page)

Table A1 (continued)

Region	Top10NL feature	Average size		% of WLF cover* detected by LiDAR-based WLF maps as ...			
		Qty	Unit	(group of) trees (in %)	hedgerow (in %)	forest patch (in %)	any WLF type (in %)
Zeeland	Trees	81	m ²	25.0	0.0	64.8	89.8
	Forest polygons	2657	m ²	1.3	2.3	80	83.6
	Tree lines	4.6	m	32.1	18.4	45.9	96.4
	Hedgerows	4.0	m	8.5	47.0	15.0	70.5
	Trees	79	m ²	19.5	2.3	72.1	93.9

Table A2

Detailed results of LiDAR WLF net change area adjustment in Limburg.

Change size category	Change	n _i	Map change area (in ha)	p _i (CI _{95%})	Adjusted change area (CI _{95%}) in ha
less than 12.57 m2	gain	10	888	0.1 (0, 0.29)	89 (0, 254)
less than 12.57 m2	loss	10	-546	0.1 (0, 0.29)	-55 (0, -156)
between 12.57 & 100 m2	gain	19	1063	0.68 (0.48, 0.89)	727 (505, 949)
between 12.57 & 100 m2	loss	18	-782	0.61 (0.39, 0.84)	-478 (-302, -654)
between 100 & 200 m2	gain	10	178	0.8 (0.55, 1)	142 (98, 178)
between 100 & 200 m2	loss	10	-269	0.8 (0.55, 1)	-215 (-148, -269)
between 200 & 1000 m2	gain	20	236	0.95 (0.85, 1)	224 (201, 236)
between 200 & 1000 m2	loss	20	-426	0.9 (0.77, 1)	-383 (-327, -426)
between 1000 m2 & 1 ha	gain	10	212	1 (1, 1)	212 (212, 212)
between 1000 m2 & 1 ha	loss	10	-333	0.9 (0.71, 1)	-300 (-238, -333)
more than 1 ha	gain	10	39	0.9 (0.71, 1)	35 (28, 39)
more than 1 ha	loss	10	-81	0.8 (0.55, 1)	-65 (-45, -81)
Total net change area			214 ^a		-350 (-470, -230)

^a Net change area obtained without removing patches in change size categories with correct change detection less than 80 % and without adjustment for false detection.

Table A3

Detailed results of LiDAR WLF net change area adjustment in Rivierenland.

Change size category	Change	n _i	Map change area (in ha)	p _i (CI _{95%})	Adjusted change area (CI _{95%}) in ha
less than 12.57 m2	gain	10	397	0.1 (0, 0.29)	40 (0, 113)
less than 12.57 m2	loss	10	-258	0.2 (0, 0.45)	-52 (0, -116)
between 12.57 & 100 m2	gain	20	692	0.6 (0.39, 0.81)	415 (267, 564)
between 12.57 & 100 m2	loss	18	-468	0.5 (0.27, 0.73)	-234 (-126, -342)
between 100 & 200 m2	gain	10	145	0.8 (0.55, 1)	116 (80, 145)
between 100 & 200 m2	loss	10	-165	1 (1, 1)	-165 (-165, -165)
between 200 & 1000 m2	gain	20	189	0.95 (0.85, 1)	180 (162, 189)
between 200 & 1000 m2	loss	20	-288	1 (1, 1)	-288 (-288, -288)
between 1000 m2 & 1 ha	gain	10	138	1 (1, 1)	138 (138, 138)
between 1000 m2 & 1 ha	loss	10	-330	1 (1, 1)	-330 (-330, -330)
more than 1 ha	gain	10	41	1 (1, 1)	41 (41, 41)
more than 1 ha	loss	10	-132	1 (1, 1)	-132 (-132, -132)
Total net change area			-2 ^a		-440 (-480, -400)

^a Net change area obtained without removing patches in change size categories with correct change detection less than 80 % and without adjustment for false detection.

Table A4

Detailed results of LiDAR WLF net change area adjustment in Zeeland.

Change size category	Change	n _i	Map change area (in ha)	p _i (CI _{95%})	Adjusted change area (CI _{95%}) in ha
less than 12.57 m2	gain	10	378	0.1 (0, 0.29)	38 (0, 108)
less than 12.57 m2	loss	10	-187	0.1 (0, 0.29)	-19 (0, -53)
between 12.57 & 100 m2	gain	19	442	0.58 (0.36, 0.8)	256 (158, 354)
between 12.57 & 100 m2	loss	19	-234	0.47 (0.25, 0.7)	-111 (-58, -164)
between 100 & 200 m2	gain	10	67	0.8 (0.55, 1)	54 (37, 67)
between 100 & 200 m2	loss	10	-77	1 (1, 1)	-77 (-77, -77)
between 200 & 1000 m2	gain	20	77	0.85 (0.69, 1)	66 (54, 77)
between 200 & 1000 m2	loss	20	-150	0.9 (0.77, 1)	-135 (-115, -150)
between 1000 m2 & 1 ha	gain	10	51	0.8 (0.55, 1)	41 (28, 51)
between 1000 m2 & 1 ha	loss	10	-156	1 (1, 1)	-156 (-156, -156)
more than 1 ha	gain	4	5	1 (1, 1)	5 (5, 5)
more than 1 ha	loss	10	-46	1 (1, 1)	-46 (-46, -46)
Total net change area			206 ^a		-248 (-279, -217)

^a Net change area obtained without removing patches in change size categories with correct change detection less than 80 % and without adjustment for false detection.

Data availability

Woody landscape features maps derived from LiDAR data are accessible on the following data repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14841121>.

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